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Management Of Physical And Environmental Hazards For Sustainable Learning Environment In Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the management of physical and environmental hazards for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State. Two (2) research questions and 2 hypotheses were answered and tested in the study, respectively. The design of the study was an analytic descriptive survey with the population as the 278 public secondary schools in Rivers State. These schools have 7827 science teachers, from which 381 (22%) were selected as a sample, using the proportionate stratified random sample sampling technique and the Taro Yamane formula. Respondents responded to a validated instrument titled Management of Physical and Environmental Hazards for Sustainable Learning Environment Questionnaire (MPEHSLEQ) designed by the researcher after the modified 4-point Likert scale model, with a reliability index of 0.80, obtained using Cronbach Alpha statistics. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions, while the z-test was used in testing the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study show that physical and environmental hazards are managed using a combination of administrative and curricular strategies, which involve students, teachers, administrators and community people. The study also established that there is a significant difference between the mean ratings of the respondents on the ways physical and environmental hazards are managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State. The study concluded that appropriate management of physical and environmental hazards guarantees a sustainable learning environment in Secondary schools in Rivers State. Consequently, it was recommended among others that School administrators and other school members should continuously use appropriate administrative strategies in managing school physical hazards as they create sustainable learning environments in schools.

Keywords: management, physical and environmental hazards, sustainable learning environment, and secondary schools.

INTRODUCTION

Secondary education occupies a strategic position in the educational structure of any society. In the educational hierarchy of any nation, it is secondary education that connects the lower level of education (primary) with the higher level (tertiary). The goals of this level of education are therefore strategic to the development of any nation. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013:14) points out that this level of education, especially at the senior level, will contribute in the following ways to the growth and development of the nation;

- a. Provide holders of the Basic Education Certificate and Junior Arabic and Islamic Studies Certificate with the opportunity for education at a higher level, irrespective of gender, social status, religious or ethnic background;
- b. offer a diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, disposition, opportunities and future roles;
- c. provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades;
- d. provide entrepreneurial, technical and vocational job-specific skills for self-reliance, and agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development;
- e. develop and promote Nigerian languages, art and culture in the context of the world's cultural heritage;
- f. inspire students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence;
- g. foster patriotism, national unity and security education with emphasis on the common ties despite our diversity; and
- h. Raise morally upright and well-adjusted individuals who can think independently and rationally, respect the views and feelings of others and appreciate the dignity of labour

The ability to achieve the stated objectives is contingent upon the structure of the learning environment. The learning environment, which encompasses both the human and material components of a school, plays a crucial role in fulfilling the goals and objectives of secondary education. A safe and comfortable school environment fosters meaningful teaching and learning, benefiting both stakeholders within the school and society as a whole. This is why various educational stakeholders invest significantly—financially, materially, and politically—in secondary education to ensure the realisation of both personal and collective educational objectives. Despite the critical importance of secondary education to different stakeholders, various educational practices within schools can jeopardise the suitability and sustainability of the educational environment, hindering the achievement of educational goals. During the execution of instructional, curricular, and co-curricular activities aimed at fulfilling these goals, certain practices may pose hazards to the safety of teachers, students, and other school users, which can ultimately undermine the educational objectives if not properly managed. These threats are commonly referred to as school hazards.

According to Wallace (2014), school hazards can take various forms, including physical and environmental hazards. These hazards, which span the different activities conducted by various school departments, can render the school unsafe for all users if not effectively managed, compromising the safety and sustainability of the learning environment.

Physical hazards refer to workplace dangers that arise in schools due to the management and handling of school materials. These hazards are often visible or tangible and can pose a risk to human health, even in the absence of physical contact. The existence of such hazards can disrupt the school environment, continually posing threats until proper order in resource handling is restored.

Environmental hazards, on the other hand, pertain to dangers that affect the natural setting of the school and, consequently, pose risks to its inhabitants. The school environment is, to some degree, naturally organised; environmental hazards emerge when actions disrupt this natural arrangement. This includes the introduction or removal of natural substances from their original positions within the school. Such disruptions can create confusion for teachers and students, negatively impacting teaching and learning activities. It is evident that educational stakeholders contribute, either directly or indirectly, to the issue of hazards within the school due to the various educational activities conducted on the premises. Therefore, effective management of these hazards is necessary to maintain a safe environment for teaching and learning. Teachers and other stakeholders must develop appropriate strategies to manage instances of school hazards within their areas of responsibility. This proactive approach will help ensure that the

school remains a safe and healthy space for achieving the educational goals and objectives outlined by the institution.

Statement of the Problem

Stakeholders in secondary schools in Rivers State have pointed out a considerable challenge linked to environmental threats that jeopardise the health and safety of teachers, students, and other individuals within the school community. This problem largely arises from inadequate management of educational resources and the irresponsible disposal of both renewable and non-renewable waste, leading to conditions that may endanger everyone involved. Acknowledging the crucial contribution of secondary education to societal growth and advancement, it is evident that achieving educational aims and objectives necessitates a suitable learning environment. Thus, it is essential for school leaders to actively tackle the physical and environmental risks that have resulted in increasing health issues among teachers and students. By formulating clear strategies and employing effective waste management methods, we can mitigate these hazards and foster a safer learning environment. Despite the commendable initiatives by the government and educational stakeholders to address these challenges, there remains significant work ahead.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study examined the management of physical and environmental hazards for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the ways physical hazards are managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State
2. Ascertain the ways environmental hazards are managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. In what ways are physical hazards managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. In what ways are environmental hazards managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following corresponding hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female science teachers on the ways physical hazards are managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State
2. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female science teachers on the ways environmental hazards are managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of School Hazard

The term "hazard" has various meanings depending on the context in which it is used. What is considered a hazard in one setting may not be viewed the same way in another. As Vazir (2009) notes, a hazard can be defined as any form of pollutant. This definition suggests that anything that disrupts an existing environmental balance can be hazardous to that environment.

Further elaborating on this, Western Sydney University (n.d.: 2) defines a hazard as any condition, situation, practice, or behaviour that has the potential to cause harm, including injury, disease, death, or damage to the environment, property, and equipment. This indicates that a hazard can be any object, event, or condition that poses a risk to individuals or organisations. In formal organisations like schools, hazards can be either natural or man-made. Hayford (2014) also emphasises that hazards are conditions in

a workplace, school, or any other organisation that can lead to temporary or permanent injuries affecting the health of teachers, students, or other stakeholders. This means that if a hazardous situation is not managed properly, it can result in either temporary or lasting damage to people or vital resources within the organisation. Therefore, a hazard represents a danger that can have short-term or long-term consequences for individuals or resources in a formal environment.

Concept of Sustainable Learning Environment

A safe and supportive learning environment is essential for achieving quality educational goals and objectives. When the environment is conducive, it motivates all educational stakeholders, encouraging them to pursue their individual and collective educational aspirations. Conversely, an unsafe learning environment can obstruct the achievement of predetermined educational goals.

Sustainability refers to the ability to meet the needs of the present while ensuring that future generations can also meet their own needs. The World Commission on Environment and Development, as cited by Elseragy, Elnokaly, and Gabr (2011), defines sustainability as the act of preserving the resources and opportunities for current and future generations. Therefore, a sustainable learning environment meets the educational needs of current students and stakeholders without compromising the educational opportunities of future learners. Achieving this sustainability requires conscious efforts to protect the school environment from deterioration and collapse.

Managing Physical Hazards for a Sustainable Learning Environment

One type of hazard that both employees and organisations can encounter is a physical hazard. As implied, physical hazards refer to any dangers present in the workplace, specifically in a school setting, that can lead to physical harm to people or damage to materials essential for achieving educational goals and objectives. This term encompasses situations where individuals sustain injuries due to objects, equipment, or materials that are improperly positioned or misused during work.

Educational scholars, such as Vicario (2012), identify physical hazards as being kinetic, electrical, pneumatic, hydraulic, or other forms. These hazards pose significant risks during a person's daily responsibilities. Therefore, managing the workspace effectively is crucial for mitigating physical hazards in any formal organisation, including schools. One common condition that leads to physical hazards in schools occurs when teachers and students work from heights or lift heavy objects. To prevent such hazards, schools should provide appropriate equipment, such as lifters, to mitigate risks associated with heights or the weight of objects used in teaching and learning. Additionally, electrical equipment can pose physical hazards, such as electric shocks and burns. Schools need to install safety signs in areas prone to electrical hazards that could negatively affect both teachers and students. Ensuring that the school's electrical wiring is correctly installed and properly maintained is also essential. Students may also face physical hazards in wet learning environments, highlighting the need for schools to employ cleaners to address these conditions. Keeping objects in appropriate locations is crucial to prevent falls. In the case of machines utilised for teaching and learning, schools should conduct regular inspections to ensure they are in good working order. Other factors contributing to physical hazards in schools include temperature, noise, and vibration.

A significant reason teachers and students often encounter physical hazards on school premises is the lack of exit points in case of a disaster. To manage risks associated with overcrowding, which can lead to stampedes, schools must ensure that there are adequate exit points for quick evacuation. Singal (2016) notes that students with disabilities are particularly vulnerable, as they may struggle to find safety during emergencies. Clear exit routes would facilitate easier evacuation for all staff and students. Furthermore, the layout and planning of the school play a crucial role in exposing staff and students to physical hazards. Poorly planned schools may contain danger spots near areas designated for teaching and learning, leading to varying degrees of physical hazards. To manage these risks, schools must prioritise effective planning and ensure that potentially hazardous structures and facilities are located far from areas accessed by staff and students.

Managing Environmental Hazards for a Sustainable Learning Environment

The school environment can be exposed to environmental hazards when educational resources are not stored properly, leading to disorderliness. Environmental hazards are defined as conditions that disrupt the natural state of the school environment. This includes placing objects in incorrect locations and contributing to pollution within the school setting. Yildiz, Yilmaz, Demir, and Toy (2011) note that some individuals face personal challenges in maintaining a safe environment at school. Therefore, it is essential to implement adequate measures to prevent environmental hazards that could impact other users of the school.

Environmental hazards can also negatively affect the health of individuals within the school, impeding their ability to fulfil their responsibilities effectively (Akomolafe, 2011). Thus, environmental hazards are viewed as the result of various other types of hazards present in the school. To manage environmental hazards and promote a sustainable learning environment, school management must ensure that regular sanitation exercises are conducted to prevent the spread of these hazards. Sanitation is crucial for creating a safe teaching and learning environment, and school management should provide the necessary sanitation equipment and experts to effectively address environmental hazards, ensuring a conducive learning atmosphere.

Theoretical Review

The school climate theory by Halphin and Croft (1963) pointed out that the school climate is the condition under which school activities are carried out. It was emphasised that it is only when the school climate is conducive that the organisation can realise its full potential. In such an organisation, the potential of all stakeholders and every resource available is used for the overall good of the organisation.

According to Halphin and Croft (1963), eight dimensions make up the climate of the school. Four of these dimensions focus on the teacher, while the other four focus on the principles of the school. The four teacher dimensions are the teacher's disengagement, hindrance, esprit and intimacy, while the four organisational principle dimensions are aloofness, production, thrust and consideration. These dimensions interplay to determine the successful accomplishment of the goals and objectives of the organisation.

This theory establishes a known fact that the school in itself is a community. However, the policies and practices established in this community will determine how the community functions. In the school system, teachers and students must collaborate with the school administrators to establish a hazard-free environment. When the climate and culture of a hazard-free school is being established, old and new teachers and students in the school will find it easy to imbibe this culture, which in the long run will be for the benefit of the teacher, students and other individuals who have direct and indirect relationships with the school.

METHODOLOGY

The design adopted for the study was the analytic descriptive survey. The population of the study comprised the 278 public secondary schools in Rivers State. These schools have 7,852 science teachers. The sample of the study was 381 science teachers drawn from the 7852 science teachers in public secondary schools in the state. They were selected using the stratified random sampling technique. Respondents' instrument titled: 'Managing Physical and Environmental Hazards for Sustainable Learning Environmental Questionnaire (MPEHSLEQ). The instrument was designed by the researcher in the modified 4-point Likert Scale model. To ensure face and content validity of the newly constructed instrument, the researcher submitted it to two experts for scrutiny and moderated the instrument. To establish the reliability coefficient of the newly constructed instrument, 20 sets of the instrument were administered to 20 teachers who did not form a part of the sample of the study and their responses were retrieved for coding and subjected to statistical analysis using Cronbach's Alpha. The use of the Cronbach Alpha was considered appropriate because it is one-time administered, dichotomously scored and makes it possible to obtain inter-item reliability. From the calculation, the scale on Physical and Environmental had 0.79 and 0.81, respectively, while the overall reliability stood at 0.80, which was considered reliable

and adequate for the study. The instrument of the study was self-administered to the respondents in their schools by the researcher, with assistance from 2 research assistants who were properly educated on their expected roles. In all, 381 copies of the instrument were distributed, while 371 (99%) were retrieved. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions, while – z-test was used in testing the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *In what ways are physical hazards managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Mean of Male and Female Science Teachers on the Ways Physical Hazards are managed for Sustainable Learning Environment in Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

S/No	Items	Male Teachers n=211 Mean \bar{X}_1	Science SD	Female Teachers n=156 Mean \bar{X}_2	Science SD	Mean Set \bar{X}	Decision
1	The provision of exit points around the school compound makes for easy escape from physical hazards	2.79	1.03	2.91	0.87	2.85	Agreed
2	Adequate plant planning in the school reduces exposure to physical hazards	2.17	1.05	2.18	0.86	2.18	Disagreed
3	Regular sensitisation of school members makes it easy to handle physical hazards around the school	2.91	1.06	2.64	0.91	2.80	Agreed
4	Changing work processes from time to time reduces the risk of physical hazards among school members	3.04	0.87	2.29	1.05	2.67	Agreed
5	Proper ventilation of the school is a measure for avoiding congestion in the school	2.28	1.23	2.18	0.91	2.23	Disagreed
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation		2.64	1.05	2.44	0.92	2.54	Agreed

Data in Table 1 show that items 1, 3, and 4 had mean ratings above the criterion mean of 2.50 and were on as the ways physical hazards are managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State. Differently, items 2 and 5 had mean ratings below the criterion mean of 2.50 and were disagreed on as the ways physical hazards are managed for sustainable learning environments in secondary schools in the state. In summary, with an aggregate mean of 2.54, above the criterion mean of 2.50, male and female teachers agreed that the ways for managing physical hazards for sustainable learning environment are adequate plant planning, regular sensitization of the school members, and

changing of work processes from time to time, while disagreed were provision of exit points, and proper ventilation of school buildings.

Research Question Two: *In what ways are environmental hazards managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings on the Ways Environmental Hazards are Managed for Sustainable Learning Environment in Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/No	Items	Male Teachers n=228 Mean \bar{X}_1 SD	Science SD	Female Teachers n=139 Mean \bar{X}_2 SD	Science SD	Mean Set X \bar{X}	Decision
6	Maintenance of waste disposal or dump sites prevents environmental hazards	3.21	1.04	3.28	0.93	3.22	Agreed
7	Access to clean water makes for environmental cleanliness in schools	2.72	1.05	2.02	1.13	2.37	Disagreed
8	Access to portable water makes for environmental cleanliness in schools	2.92	1.02	2.22	1.06	2.39	Agreed
9	The provision of surveillance equipment makes it easy to monitor the use of the school environment	2.19	1.05	2.35	0.91	1.61	Disagreed
10	The provision of surveillance equipment makes it easy to ensure healthy school usage	3.43	1.01	3.21	1.15	3.27	Agreed
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation		2.89	1.03	2.62	1.04	2.76	Agreed

Data in Table 2 show that items 6,8, and 10 had mean ratings above the criterion mean of 2.50 and were agreed as the ways for managing environmental hazards for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State. Differently, items 7 and 9 had mean ratings below the criterion mean of 2.50 and were disagreed upon as the ways for managing environmental hazards in secondary schools in Rivers State. In summary, with an aggregate weighted mean of 2.76 above the criterion mean of 2.50, male and female science teachers agreed that the ways for managing environmental hazards for sustainable learning environment are Maintenance of waste disposal or dump sites prevent environmental hazard, access to portable water, Provision of surveillance equipment makes it easy to ensure healthy school usage. While Access to clean water makes for environmental cleanliness in schools, and provision of surveillance equipment was disagreed upon.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female science teachers on the ways physical hazards are managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State

Table 3: Summary of Z-test Analysis of the Difference between the Mean Ratings of Male and Female Science Teachers on the Ways Physical Hazards are Managed for Sustainable Learning Environment in Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	n	Mean	SD	df	z-cal.	Z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Male Science Teachers	211	2.64	1.05	365	2.34	1.96	0.05	Not Accepted
Female Science Teachers	156	2.44	0.92					

Data in Table 3 shows the value of z-cal. To be 2.34 while the value of z-crit. Was 1.96. Since the value of z-cal. Of 2.34 is greater than the values of z-crit. Of 1.96, the null hypothesis was not accepted, and this implied that there is a significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female science teachers on the ways physical hazards are managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female science teachers on the ways environmental hazards are managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State

Table 4: summary of z-test Analysis of the Difference between the Mean Ratings of male and female Science Teachers on the Ways Environmental Hazards are Managed for Sustainable Learning Environment in Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	n	Mean	SD	df	z-cal.	Z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Male Science Teachers	228	2.89	1.03	365	2.42	1.96	0.05	Not Accepted
Female Science Teachers	139	2.62	1.04					

Data in Table 4 shows the value of z-cal. Of 2.42 was more than the value of z-crit. Of 1.96 and as such, the null hypothesis was not accepted, and this implied that there is a significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female science teachers on the ways environmental hazards are managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS/IMPLICATIONS

Managing Physical Hazards for Sustainable Learning Environment in Secondary Schools in Rivers State

The first finding of the study is that the ways for managing physical hazards for a sustainable learning environment are adequate plant planning, regular sensitisation of the school members, and changing work processes from time to time, while disagreements were provision of exit points, and proper ventilation of school buildings. Also, a corresponding finding from a test of hypothesis establishes a significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female science teachers on the ways physical hazards are managed for a sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings align with the studies conducted by Arop, Owan, and Ekpan (2018), as well as Gbadago, Amedone, and Honyenugu (2017), and

Bakir, Babayisit, Tekbas, Ogur, Kilie, and Ulus (2014), which indicate that physical hazards are managed in identified ways. A possible explanation for this may be that schools have recently focused more on managing physical hazards. These findings suggest that schools with a sustainable learning environment are those that effectively manage physical hazards.

Managing Environmental Hazards for a Sustainable Learning Environment in Secondary Schools in Rivers State

The second findings of the study showed ways for managing environmental hazards for a sustainable learning environment are the Maintenance of waste disposal or dump sites to prevent environmental hazards, access to portable water, Provision of surveillance equipment makes it easy to ensure healthy school usage. While Access to clean water makes for environmental cleanliness in schools, and provision of surveillance equipment was disagreed. Also, a corresponding finding from a test of hypothesis established a significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the ways environmental hazards are managed for the sustainable learning environment in secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings align with the studies conducted by Sarfraz, Qun, Hui, and Abdulah (2018), Sahar, Hemat, and Emad (2019), as well as Ogbonna and Bosong (2018), which provide insights on managing environmental hazards from this perspective. One possible explanation for these findings is that, given the deteriorating school environments in the state due to their topography, school leaders have developed strategies to address hazards arising from their surroundings. This suggests that schools with a sustainable learning environment actively engage in effective management of their surroundings.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the discussions on them and their educational implication, it is concluded that appropriate management of physical and environmental hazards guarantees a sustainable learning environment in Secondary School in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the conclusion of the study, it is recommended as follows:

1. School administrators and other school members should continuously use appropriate administrative strategies in managing school physical hazards they make sustainable learning environments in schools
2. School administrators and other stakeholders in school administration should continue to make use of existing strategies in managing environmental hazards while also exploring new strategies to ensure a sustainable learning environment in schools.

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